

Optical and electrical performance of translucent BaTiO₃-BaSnO₃ ceramics

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Abstract

Lead-free piezoceramic with the composition of 0.89BaTiO₃-0.11BaSnO₃ (BT-11BS) was prepared by solid-state reaction followed by conventional sintering achieving nearly full density. The influence of sintering temperature on electrical properties were thoroughly investigated, implying a significant role in achieving best properties, which were obtained between 1420-1440 °C. The addition of SnO₂ in BaTiO₃ solid solution promoted grain growth, eventually resulting in the grain sizes between 145-216 μm. An ultra-high dielectric permittivity $> 5.0 \times 10^4$ and related dielectric loss of 3.1% at $\sim 40^\circ$ C was achieved. A high value of quasi-static piezoelectric constant (d_{33}) of 693 pC/N and the converse piezoelectric constant (denoted as d_{33}^*) reached a value of up to 831 pm/V in the frequency range between 10-110 Hz. The transmittance of $\sim 25\%$ in the visible region and $\sim 40\%$ in the infrared region together with good electromechanical properties showcasing a unique combination for this material.

1. Introduction

Translucent piezoelectrics are advantageous materials for various ultrasound optical instruments ranging from photoacoustic transducers to actuators [1]. Traditional transducers made from ferroelectric ceramics such as Pb(Zr,Ti)O₃ (PZT) with a composition close to the morphotropic phase boundary (MPB) show outstanding piezoelectric performance. However, the toxicity of lead (Pb) to both humans and the environment has been well documented. [2] Therefore, the European union legislation advocated the eradication of lead-based material [3]. LiNbO₃ crystals and polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) polymers are now commonly used, but they exhibit much lower d_{33} and k_{33} values [4, 5], limiting the acoustic source levels, bandwidths, and sensitivity of transducers.

Due to their excellent piezoelectric properties and environmental friendliness barium titanate (BT) is one of the most common lead-free alternatives [6]. Piezoelectric properties of BT ceramics were improved by

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4 applying various sintering techniques, such as microwave sintering [7], hot pressing [8] and spark plasma
5 sintering [9]. The perovskite structure of BT can be tailored by B-site engineering, using different dopants,
6 to further increase its functional properties. Among the possible dopants, tin oxide (SnO_2) became one of
7 the most interesting ones, by Sn^{4+} replacing Ti^{4+} at B-site. Such system could potentially acquire
8 exceptionally high piezoelectric constant, large relative permittivity, improved energy storage properties as
9 well as required optical and photoluminescent properties. Indeed, a giant piezoelectric coefficient $d_{33} >$
10 1100 pC/N is achieved in Sn-doped BaTiO_3 (BTS_x) ($x=0.11$) ceramics, which is the the highest value
11 reported for lead-free ceramics, which was ascribed linked to the strategic design of a flat Gibbs free energy
12 density profile via a synergistic approach that involves both coexistence of multiple phases and local
13 structural heterogeneity [10]. As proposed by Yao et al. [11], $0.89\text{BaTiO}_3\text{-}0.11\text{BaSnO}_3$ (in the following
14 text denoted as BT-11BS) shows a coexistence of cubic-tetragonal-orthorhombic-rhombohedral (C-T-O-
15 R) phases termed as quasi-quadruple point (Q_P) near 40°C , which could be the reason for the observed
16 obtaining excellent piezoelectric properties ($d_{33} = 697 \text{ pC/N}$). Gao et al. [12] found a multiphase co-existence
17 point for $0.895\text{BaTiO}_3\text{-}0.105\text{BaSnO}_3$ composition, resulting in an outstanding dielectric permittivity ($\epsilon_r =$
18 5.4×10^4) and low dielectric loss of 3.9% near 37°C . Zahid et al. [13] shows the potential of $\text{BaTi}_{0.89}\text{Sn}_{0.11}\text{O}_3$
19 ceramic system in solid state cooling technology (electrocaloric responsivity ($\Delta T/\Delta E$) = 0.24 K.mm/kV)
20 and high energy storage applications (storage density = 122 mJ/cm^2) near ambient temperature. Moreover,
21 one of the other lead-free piezoceramic composition of $x\text{Sm}\text{-}(1-x)\text{K}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{NbO}_3$ (where, $x = 2 \text{ mol\%}$ and
22 sample thickness $\sim 0.4 \text{ mm}$) showed revealed excellent transparency $\sim 60\%$ and $\sim 71\%$ at 800nm and
23 1600nm , respectively [14]. On the other hand, $x\text{Nd}\text{-}(1-x)\text{K}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{NbO}_3$ (where, $x = 0.3 \text{ mol\%}$ and sample
24 thickness $\sim 0.3 \text{ mm}$) resulted in 28% of transparency with the presence of absorption peak and 35%
25 otherwise at 800 nm , and $\sim 46\%$ while at 1600 nm [15]. In addition, Pithan et al., [16] were able to show
26 optical transmittance of $\sim 29\%$ (sample thickness of 0.78 mm) for $\text{BaTiO}_3\text{-}2\text{mol.\%La}$ material. While
27 having lucrative transparent aspect, the above mentioned doped- $\text{K}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{NbO}_3$ or, doped-BT based
28 research were was unable to show piezoelectric behavior at the same time.

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46 CurrentlyRecently, the capabilities of the $\text{BaTiO}_3\text{-BaSnO}_3$ material system to achieve a high piezoelectric
47 constant, dielectric constant and required energy storage properties were studied [11-18]. However,
48 preparing synthesizing this material with a translucency of $\geq 20\%$ while and maintaining excellent good
49 dielectric and piezoelectric properties could be challenging. Such a combination of properties could
50 potentially open a door for fabricating a translucent piezoelectric and/or dielectric material, useful for
51 supercapacitors as well as sensor and actuator applications. To the best of our knowledge literature
52 exploration, $\text{BaTiO}_3\text{-BaSnO}_3$ material system with excellent piezo and dielectric properties and desired
53 optical performance has not been reported so far.
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4 In the current study, we prepared the BT-11BS $0.89\text{BaTiO}_3 - 0.11\text{BaSnO}_3$ was fabricated by conventional
5 solid-state reaction followed by pressure-less sintering in air. We demonstrated the effect of sample
6 thickness, sintering temperature, density, and grain size on the phase composition, optical properties, and
7 dielectric and piezoelectric electrical properties that which may give insight for improving the performance
8 of this material system.
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10 11 12 13 **2. Experiment and methods**

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15 To prepare $0.89\text{BaTiO}_3 - 0.11\text{BaSnO}_3$, the starting powders BaCO_3 (99.5%; Dakram; particle size $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$),
16 TiO_2 (99.5%; Dakram; particle size $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$) and SnO_2 (99.9%; Sigma Aldrich; particle size $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$) were
17 dried at $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/2 \text{ h}$ before weighing and mixing according to their stoichiometric ratios. The raw powders
18 were mixed in a horizontal ball mill in ethanol for 24 h, using zirconia milling balls, and then dried at $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
19 for 12 h. The weight ratio of powder, milling media, and ethanol was 1:2:2. The mixed powder was then
20 calcined at $1200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/4 \text{ h}$ at a heating and cooling rate of $3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. After that, the heat-treated powder was
21 again milled in ethanol for 10 hours to crush the agglomerates and two binders (Duramax B1000 and B1007,
22 Chesham Chemicals, UK, 2 wt.% each) were added during the last hour of milling. The resultant slurry was
23 dried and then sieved using a $300 \mu\text{m}$ screen (VWR, UK). The particle size distribution of mixed powders
24 was measured by laser diffraction (LA-950, Horiba, Japan). The green bodies 13 mm in diameter and over
25 0.5 mm and $\sim 1 \text{ mm}$ of thickness were produced by uniaxial pressing at the pressure of 150 MPa. The
26 binders were removed from the green specimens by annealing at $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/1 \text{ h}$ in air. Finally, the specimens
27 were sintered in the air using a conventional furnace (Clasic, Czech Republic) at different sintering
28 temperatures ranging from $1380 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $1440 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 h at a heating and cooling rate of $3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.
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33 The XRD patterns (Rigaku Smart Lab, Japan) were obtained at room temperature (RT) using a
34 diffractometer with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) Ni-filtered radiation. The diffraction patterns were recorded with
35 the scan resolution of 0.0002° in the 2θ range of $10^\circ - 145^\circ$ using a counting speed $4^\circ/\text{min}$. The working
36 current and voltage were 10 mA and 40 kV, respectively. The Rietveld refinements of the diffraction
37 patterns of sintered BT-11BS ceramics were performed using the PDXL software using two different
38 crystallographic information file (CIF) standards. The CIF files originating from XRD analyses deposited
39 on Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC): CCDC995537 for cubic phase and CCDC995538 for
40 tetragonal phase were used for $\text{BaSn}_x\text{Ti}_{(1-x)}\text{O}_3$ ceramics, where $x = 0.10$. Relative density was measured by
41 Archimedes method (EN 623-2) and then expressed as a percentage of the theoretical density (TD) of 6.15
42 g/cm^3 obtained from XRD results. The grain size was estimated by linear intercept method (EN 623-3) from
43 scanning electron micrographs (SEM, Verios 460L, Thermo Fisher, Czech Republic) of polished and
44 thermally etched samples. The thermal etching was carried out at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ below the sintering temperature
45 with a heating and cooling rate of $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and 10 min holding time. The average grain size was calculated
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4 from the 5 measurements each of three different SEM pictures at for each sintering temperature. The
5 correction factor for grain size ($G \times 1.56$) was taken into consideration [19] and the number of measured
6 grains were approximately 200. The same micrographs were used for grain boundary density calculation
7 using image analysis (the Gwyddion software, version 2.57). The photoluminescence (PL) spectra were
8 collected at the WITec confocal Raman imaging system (Alpha300 R, Witec, Germany) at room
9 temperature (RT) using 355 nm laser irradiation and 4 mW power. The integration time was 10 s and the
10 number of accumulations was 10. The total forward transmittance (hereafter transmittance) of sintered and
11 plain parallelly polished samples with the nominal thicknesses of 0.5 and 1.0 mm was measured with a UV-
12 VIS spectrophotometer (Specord 250 Plus, Analytik Jena AG, Germany). The spectrophotometer was
13 equipped with an integrating sphere with a diameter of 75 mm. Each sample was analyzed five times in the
14 wavelength range 300-1100 nm, and the mean light transmittance was evaluated. The refractive indices and
15 extinction coefficients were obtained from ellipsometry spectra acquired with a rotating analyzer
16 ellipsometer (V-VASE, J.A. Woollam, USA). The ellipsometry measurements were performed in the 190-
17 1100 nm wavelength range (~ 1.1 -6.5 eV), at RT and at three angles of incidence (65° , 70° and 75°) to
18 obtain the highest sensitivity. The WVASE32 software (J.A. Woollam, USA) was used for fitting and
19 extracting the measured and calculated data.
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32 The dielectric properties (measured at 1 KHz) and small signal converse piezoelectric constant (triangular
33 wave function; 25 V; at 1000, 500, 250, 110, 10 Hz) were calculated by a piezoelectric evaluation system
34 (aixPES, aixACCT systems, Germany) on sintered samples. High amplitude signal (defining hysteresis
35 loop points) was modified by small amplitude signal of high frequency (1kHz) used for the calculation of
36 converse piezoelectric signal as a local value for each point of the loop. The positive values at zero field in
37 the piezoelectric loops (i.e. in non-switching branch of the loop) were acquired as the small signal d_{33}
38 (denoted as d_{33}^* in the current study). The quasi-static direct piezoelectric constant (d_{33}) was measured by
39 Berlincourt d_{33} meter (ZJ-3C, Institute of Acoustics, Academia Sinica, China) on the samples poled in
40 silicon oil at 3 kV/mm for 10 min.
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47 **3. Results and discussions**

48 **3.1 Particle size prior to shaping and sintering**

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50 The particle size distribution of prepared BT-11BS ceramic powders is shown in Fig. 1. The distribution
51 of particle size is unimodal and the mean particle size was measured to be $\sim 4.5 \mu\text{m}$. This value is slightly
52 above the initial powders' size indicating mild agglomeration during milling.
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3.2 Microstructural Characteristics

Fig. 2(a-d) shows representative microstructures of BT-11BS ceramics after sintering at different temperatures. Small pores were observed in the SEM micrographs of all thermally etched samples. The extremely accelerated grain growth was observed - the grain size increased from initial 4.5 μm up to 145 μm (at 1380 $^{\circ}\text{C}$)-216 μm (at 1440 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). To the best of our knowledge, such extreme grain growth has never not been reported so far for the BT-11BS ceramics. The relative density ranged from 96.8 to 97.6 % TD, while zero open porosity was detected in the samples. The relative density and grain size as a function of sintering temperature are depicted in Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b, respectively. The grain boundary density G_{BD} was calculated from SEM micrographs as a sum of grain boundary lengths divided by the area. The G_{BD} continuously decreased from 20.9 mm^{-1} to 15.5 mm^{-1} for samples sintered at 1380 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 1440 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is consistent with the determined grain sizes. Furthermore, it is well known that the size of particles can have a significant impact on the sintering behavior of ceramics. When the particle size is smaller, the driving force for sintering is higher, allowing for lower sintering temperatures. Our previous research [20] has demonstrated that ceramics with a particle size of 1 μm , achieve a density of over 96% at a temperature of ~ 1350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, whereas particle sizes ranging from 3 to 5 μm require temperatures of 1425 to 1500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. These findings align with our current study, where we have achieved a relative density of over 96% within the temperature range of 1380 - 1440 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ using particles with a size of 4.5 μm .

Wang and Liu [21] showed that the addition of a small amount of SnO_2 (0.4-1.6%) to BCZT ceramics could accelerate grain growth due to the high concentration of O-vacancies resulting from the Sn addition. It can be thus suggested that Sn^{4+} acted as a B-site acceptor impurity that yielded oxygen (O)-vacancies also in the present work, similarly to the report by Smyth et al. [22] that showed such unavoidable acceptor impurities may result in development of O-vacancies. O-vacancies are also known to form in samples annealed at higher temperature (>1300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) due to the evaporation of O [23]. The extensive grain growth observed in this work can be thus attributed to the greater mass transport induced by O-vacancies, which was derived from the SnO_2 incorporation in the BaTiO_3 material system [24].

3.3 X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis

The XRD patterns of BT-11BS ceramics sintered at different temperatures are shown in Fig. 4. For Rietveld refinement, the standard CIF files originating from XRD of $\text{BaSn}_x\text{Ti}_{(1-x)}\text{O}_3$ with the nominal value $x=0.10$ were used. To the best of our knowledge our search, no better suitable standards are currently available. The Rietveld refinement results are summarized in Table 1, showing co-existence of both tetragonal and cubic phase. The amount of cubic phase increased with increasing sintering temperature. For instance, the content of cubic phase increased from $\sim 19\%$ to 51% with the increase of the sintering temperature from

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4 1380 °C to 1440 °C. In addition, the decrease in the c/a ratio implies the reduction in the tetragonality with
5 the sintering temperatures increasing from 1400 °C to 1440 °C.
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8 3.4 Photoluminescence (PL) spectra 9

10 The PL spectra for BT-11BS ceramics over a spectral range of 355-800 nm were acquired at RT using
11 irradiation by a 355 nm laser (Fig. 5). A broad green PL band between 450-600 nm is attributed to the
12 presence of point defects and oxygen vacancies due to charge-transfer of singly ionized oxygen vacancy
13 and the charge-transfer vibronic excitons [25]. The lowest PL intensities belong to the samples sintered at
14 1420 °C and 1440 °C. These samples have the largest grain size (~ 214-216 μm), which suggests that the
15 grain boundaries also contribute to the PL radiation. The correlation between the PL intensity and the grain
16 size confirms defect-related nature of the emission. Grain boundaries can act as additional dislocation
17 centers and in-gap states. This fact is also supported by the difference in PL intensities of samples sintered
18 at 1400 °C and 1420 °C. The rise of the emission peaks near 700 nm (more pronounced at lower sintering
19 temperatures) is attributed to Ti defects in the perovskite matrix [26]. The decrease of PL intensity with
20 increasing sintering temperature indicates the suppression of recombination caused by structural changes
21 or disorder as also shown previously [27]. The shift of photoluminescent peaks to lower wavelengths can
22 be ascribed to the transition from tetragonal to cubic phase [25]. An irregular change tendency with sintering
23 temperature could be explained by variation of several parameters under sintering (phase changes,
24 crystalline disorder, grain size). The observed trend is explained by the assumption that the samples'
25 luminescence is the result of different excitation mechanisms: distorted structure and defects mechanism,
26 electrical field mechanism, structure, and morphology mechanism, etc. [28] The broad band shape confirms
27 multiphoton nature of the PL. But more significant excitation mechanism in the studied samples belongs to
28 higher concentration of defects originated from larger surface area of the samples with smaller grains. In
29 this case, the ordered [TiO₆] clusters in large grains are substituted by complex forms of disordered [TiO₅]
30 clusters responsible for the photoluminescence emission [29].
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46 3.5 Transmittance and reflectance 47

48 Fig. 6 shows the transmittance of polished samples with a thickness of 0.5 mm and ~ 1 mm at different
49 wavelengths of the light spectrum (exact thicknesses are specified in Table 2 below). The shadowed area
50 depicts the visible light range. The content of tetragonal phase in BT-11BS ceramics decreased steadily
51 with the increasing sintering temperature and the cubic phase became dominant. A higher light
52 transmittance can be thus expected for samples sintered at higher temperatures. This, however, was not
53 confirmed, possibly due the presence of residual porosity in the samples, which strongly affected the light
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4 Reflectance R, and maximum theoretical transmittance, T_{th} , for a light beam perpendicular to the sample
5 surface were calculated using Eq. (1) and (2)
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$$R = \frac{(n - 1)^2 + k^2}{(n + 1)^2 + k^2} \times 100, \quad (1)$$

$$T_{th} = \frac{(1 - R/100)^2 e^{-\alpha t}}{1 - (R/100)^2 e^{-2\alpha t}} \times 100, \quad (2)$$

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16 where n is the refractive index, k is extinction coefficient, α is the absorption coefficient and t is the sample
17 thickness. Eq. 1 is the well-known Fresnel equation. Eq. 2 is valid for the homogeneously absorbing sample,
18 assuming that the light beam has zero deflection from the direction of the incident light. The refractive
19 index of BT-11BS samples sintered at different temperatures was measured by optical interferometry and
20 is listed in Table 2 together with other optical coefficients. The beam intensity loss from the sample surface
21 (measured at 600 nm) caused by reflection varied from 12.1-14.4 % and was ascribed to the small changes
22 in refractive indices ($n = 2.0$ - 2.2). The beam intensity loss by reflection of other piezoceramics such as
23 $BaTiO_3$ [30], 0.45BCT-0.55BZT [31], $(Ba,La)TiO_3$ [16] were previously reported in the range 16.5-17.2%.
24 If we consider maximum theoretical transmittance, T_{th} around 78.4 % (shown in Fig. 6 as a dashed
25 horizontal straight line), the transmittance of 51 and 38% T_{th} can be achieved in the IR region (at 1100 nm)
26 and 25 and 6% T_{th} in the visible region (at 600 nm) for the different nominal thickness of 0.5 and 1 mm,
27 respectively.
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37 Such optical properties are reported for the $BaSnTiO_3$ material reported in the present study for the first
38 time. In our previous work [32], BCZT piezoelectric material system with the a low piezoelectric constant
39 of 145 pC/N achieved ~ 40% transmittance (measured at 750 nm) at the sample thickness of ~ 0.5 mm.
40 However, in the current study, conventional sintering was used instead of spark plasma sintering (SPS).
41 Er^{3+} and $K_{0.5}Na_{0.5}NbO_3$ (KNN) modified BCZT ceramic was reported to achieve up to 40% transmittance
42 (sample thickness ~ 0.3 mm) at 780 nm and 48% at 1600 nm, but the electrical properties were not measured
43 [33]. For $(Ba_{0.99}La_{0.01})Ti_{1.005}O_3$ material, the normalized transmittance value reached up to 29% (sample
44 thickness = 0.78 mm) at 800 nm [31] only merely showing ferroelectric hysteresis (Remanent polarization,
45 $P_r = 4.18 \mu C/cm^2$). Another work on $BaTiO_3$ ceramics reported the transmittance of 32% at 800 nm, but for
46 comparatively much thinner sample of 0.2 mm showing with a low $P_r = 2 \mu C/cm^2$ and the dielectric constant
47 of 1500 [34]. In comparison to the BT- based ceramics, KNN showed the transmittance of 22 % at 800 nm
48 and 57 % at 1600 nm (sample thickness = 0.3 mm) with $d_{33} = 55$ pC/N, $P_r = 16 \mu C/cm^2$, and the dielectric
49 constant of 881 [35]. In general, the reports on lead-free electroceramics show indicate that a combination
50 of translucency with good electrical properties is are rare. The BT-11BS material prepared in this study
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4 outperforms all previous reports in terms of high piezoelectric constant, ultra-high dielectric constant along
5 with the transmittance of up to 25% at 700 nm and ~ 40% at > 900 nm. Also note that the high transmittance
6 values of the BT-11BS material prepared in this work were measured on comparatively thicker samples
7 (0.5 mm) than in other reports. A detailed discussion of the electrical properties of the studied BT-11BS
8 material system can be found in the following subsequent sections.
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14 3.6 Dielectric properties

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16 Fig 7 (a) shows temperature dependence of dielectric permittivity (ϵ_r) in the range of 20-70 °C for BSnT
17 BT-11BS ceramics sintered at different sintering temperatures. The maximum dielectric permittivity
18 ($\epsilon_{r(\max)}$) at the Curie temperature ($T_C \sim 43$ °C) as well as the ϵ_r at RT (~ 24 °C) were higher in for the samples
19 sintered at higher temperatures. The $\epsilon_{r(\max)}$ value reached a maximum of $\sim 5.1 \times 10^4$ at the near room
20 temperature ~ 43 °C when sintered at 1440 °C (Fig. 7(b)). The similar value of ϵ_r value was found reported
21 by Gao et al. [11] previously. The ϵ_r values acquired in our study are approximately 5 times larger than the
22 relative permittivity of a pure BaTiO₃ ceramics at its Curie temperature T_C . A low dielectric loss in the
23 range of 2.7-3.1% was also recorded (Fig. 7(c)). Fig. 7 (d) shows that both the ϵ_r and dielectric loss ($\tan \delta$)
24 was increased increasing with the increasing grain size. It should be noted that such a high ϵ_r is beneficial
25 for the performance of energy storage devices especially at finite field strength. Previously, a large dielectric
26 response was reported for both the ferroelectric quasi-quadruple point i.e., cubic-tetragonal-orthorhombic-
27 rhombohedral (C-T-O-R) [11] and the tricritical point (O-T-R) [12] in BaTiO₃-BaSnO₃. Previously, It was
28 shown that the small addition of SnO₂ ($x = 0.016$) in BCZT ceramic shifts the O-T phase transition to a
29 higher temperature (from 30 °C to 45 °C), while T-C phase transition is shifted to a lower temperature
30 (from 96 °C to 72 °C) [19]. In this study, it might be possible that the shift of both transition peaks towards
31 each other is large enough due to much higher SnO₂ content used, possibly overlapping each other that
32 results resulting in a single dielectric permittivity peak.
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45 Although all samples sintered at various temperatures have identical phase composition and similar density,
46 grain size cannot be neglected also play an important role in achieving optimal dielectric properties
47 performance in BT-based piezoceramics [20]. The samples sintered at 1420 °C and 1440 °C with the grain
48 sizes ~ 214-216 μm have higher ϵ_r values and comparatively sharp permittivity peaks at T-C phase
49 transition. The samples sintered at 1380 °C and 1400 °C with a comparatively smaller grain size (~ 145-
50 151 μm) show illustrate broader permittivity peaks and lower ϵ_r values. Particularly, as shown in Fig. 8 (a,
51 b), the frequency dispersion becomes more distinct for the samples with the grain size ~ 145-151 μm , where
52 $\epsilon_{r(\max)}$ decreases with increasing frequency. The evaluation of frequency dispersion indicates that the
53 permittivity peaks are broader for the ceramics with smaller grain size. In addition, full width half maximum
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(FWHM) values of 0.33, 0.34, 0.25 and 0.25 radians further support that the broadening of peaks are also correlated to grain size.

A modified empirical expression proposed by Uchino and Nomura [36] was employed in the current study to further characterize the dielectric dispersion and diffusivity (γ) of the phase transition. The Curie-Weiss law for the calculation of γ may be expressed as follows:

$$1 / \epsilon_r - 1/\epsilon_{r(\max)} = (T - T_{\max})^\gamma / C, \text{ with } (T > T_{\max}), \quad (3)$$

where T_{\max} is the temperature at which the maximum relative permittivity is achieved, while γ and C are constants with the values varying between 1 and 2. The value of $\gamma = 1$ makes the equation fit of Curie-Weiss law for the classic first order normal ferroelectrics, whereas $\gamma = 2$ describes the ideal relaxor ferroelectric behaviour. The γ values for the samples sintered at 1380 °C and 1400 °C calculated from the slope of the linear fit in the paraelectric phase region were found to be 1.95 and 1.86, respectively (Fig. 9), which indicates that the nature of BSnT BT-11BS samples at lower sintering temperatures is close to that of a relaxor. With the increase of grain size, γ values decreased to ~ 1.68 . The diffusivity values are in accordance with the frequency dispersion of the dielectric permittivity peaks. This indicates that the reduction in grain size tends to enhance relaxor nature, which may be partly related to the domain refinement and weakening of long-range ferroelectric interactions [37]. However, the splitting of dielectric permittivity curves above T_C persists (Fig. 8a) for the materials sintered at 1380 °C and 1400 °C, despite the diffusivity coefficient $\gamma = 1.95$ indicating almost regular relaxor behaviour. This implies the existence of dipole clusters in the paraelectric phase at temperatures close to T_C , which could be correlated to the increased content of tetragonal phase (T) in the T-C structure (Table 1) and the finer grain size.

3.7 Piezoelectric properties

Fig. 10 (a) shows piezoelectric constant (d_{33}) measured by quasi-static method plotted against the sintering temperature. The effect of sintering temperature and therefore the grain size on d_{33} was significant: d_{33} increased from 412 pC/N (1380 °C) to a maximum of 693 pC/N (1420 °C) and then stabilized with further increase in sintering temperature. This could be related to the sharp increase in the grain size from $\sim 145 \mu\text{m}$ (1380 °C) to $\sim 216 \mu\text{m}$ (1420 °C).

Small signal converse piezoelectric constant, d_{33}^* , calculated from the field-dependent piezoelectric loops, follows the same trend (Fig. 10(b)). However, the measurement frequency holds also significant an influence on achieving the large d_{33}^* values. The d_{33}^* continuously increased with decreasing frequency, irrespective of the sintering temperatures. The d_{33}^* values were similar for all sintering temperatures between 10 Hz and 110 Hz. The d_{33}^* values between 640 - 730 pm/V were measured for the samples sintered between 1380 °C-1400 °C and 798-831 pm/V when sintered at 1420 °C-1440 °C. This large

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4 piezoelectric response may be ascribed to the anisotropic flattening of the energy profile granting access to
5 a low energy barrier for polarization rotation [16]. The planar coupling coefficient (k_p) and the mechanical
6 quality factor (Q_m) are shown in Fig. 10c.
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10 Another important aspect is the grain size of the BT-11BS ceramics. If grain size is considered one might
11 ask how large is 'large enough' to achieve the best piezoelectric properties? It is well known that any
12 specific piezoelectric ceramic composition is characteristic by an optimal grain size range where the best
13 properties are achieved. For pure BaTiO_3 [9], $\text{K}(\text{Na},\text{Nb})\text{O}_3$ [38], $(\text{Ba},\text{Ca})(\text{Zr},\text{Ti})\text{O}_3$ [39], and
14 $(\text{Ba},\text{Ca})(\text{Sn},\text{Ti})\text{O}_3$ [40], the values of $\sim 1\text{-}3.5\ \mu\text{m}$, $\sim 1.4\text{-}7.1\ \mu\text{m}$, $\sim 20\text{-}30\ \mu\text{m}$ and $\sim 40\text{-}56\ \mu\text{m}$ were reported
15 respectively, as the optimal grain size range for the enhanced piezo performance. Therefore, 'optimum'
16 grain size would be a more appropriate term than 'large' grain size, because the values related to the term
17 'large' differ for different piezoelectric compositions. In the current study, the d_{33} and d_{33}^* values increased
18 more or less linearly with increasing grain size (Fig. 11(a,b)). Since the sintering temperature $> 1440\ ^\circ\text{C}$
19 caused partial melting of the BT-11BS samples, the optimum grain size for which an enhanced electro-
20 mechanical performance was observed for the BT-11BS ceramics prepared in this study was around $\sim 214\text{-}$
21 $216\ \mu\text{m}$.
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31 Fig. 12 illustrates displacement as a function of applied voltage from which normalization coefficient
32 ($S_{\text{max}}/E_{\text{max}}$) was evaluated for each sample. Presented unipolar loops were measured at 1 Hz frequency. The
33 $S_{\text{max}}/E_{\text{max}}$ values fluctuate between 782 to 934 pm/V and there was no obvious trend seen. Normalization
34 coefficient values $S_{\text{max}}/E_{\text{max}}$ are calculated as average values of unipolar loop slope in non-switching field
35 range in Fig. 12. This might show different values of piezoelectric coefficient d_{33}^* and therefore also its
36 dependency on the sintering temperature compared to Fig. 10 (b), where the piezoelectric coefficient values
37 are calculated at one point of the loop (zero field) and at higher frequency than 1 Hz. However, correlation
38 between small grain size, higher degree of relaxor nature may also play an important role in achieving
39 optimum $S_{\text{max}}/E_{\text{max}}$ value as for the sample sintered at $1400\ ^\circ\text{C}$. The highest value was obtained at $1400\ ^\circ\text{C}$
40 which could be due to the correlation between small grain size, higher degree of relaxor nature and
41 comparatively thinner sample (see table 2). Both intrinsic and extrinsic contributions define piezoelectricity
42 and therefore, regardless of measurement approach, the intrinsic contribution should be at the same level,
43 while the extrinsic contribution is sensitive to external excitations [41]. The larger extrinsic contribution
44 from the domain wall motion to the response of piezoelectric strain measurement may possibly be the
45 source of large values of $S_{\text{max}}/E_{\text{max}}$.
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Conclusion

The lead-free ceramic composition of $0.89\text{BaTiO}_3 - 0.11\text{BaSnO}_3$ (BT-11BS) was prepared through a solid-state reaction route and subsequently underwent conventional sintering. The effect of sintering temperature and grain size on electrical and optical properties were evaluated and the sintering temperature between $1420\text{-}1440\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ were detected as optimal. The material exhibited high dielectric permittivity exceeding 5.0×10^4 , accompanied by a minimal dielectric loss of 3.1% at approximately $40\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. These dielectric properties surpass those of most commercially available dielectric ceramics. Furthermore, at room temperature ($\sim 24\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), the material demonstrated a considerable quasi-static piezoelectric constant (d_{33}) reaching a value of 693 pC/N . The indirect piezoelectric constant (d_{33}^*) achieved a value up to 831 pm/V in the frequency range between $10\text{-}110\text{ Hz}$. Notably, the material exhibited a transmittance of approximately 25% in the visible and $\sim 40\%$ in the infrared regions. These good electromechanical properties combined with translucent characteristics for BT-11BS material composition, present an intriguing opportunity for further research and exploration, aiming to unlock the full potential of the $\text{BaTiO}_3\text{-BaSnO}_3$ material system.

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Data availability statements

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available in the repository, [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10209807>].

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4 **Figure captions**
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6 Fig. 1 Particle size distribution of BT-11BS ceramics after calcination and re-milling
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8 Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of BT-11BS ceramics at different sintering temperatures
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10 Fig. 3 (a) Relative density and, (b) grain size dependence on sintering temperature for BT-11BS ceramics
11 Vertical bars denote standard deviations of the measurements
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13 Fig. 4 X-ray diffraction patterns of BT-11BS ceramics after sintering at different sintering temperatures
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15 Fig. 5 Photoluminescence spectra of BT-11BS ceramics
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17 Fig. 6 Light transmittance (averaged) of BT-11BS samples with the nominal thicknesses of 0.5 and 1.0 mm.
18 The inset represents camera shot of the real light transmittance of 0.5 mm thick samples placed directly on
19 the background, sintered at 1420 °C/4h
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22 Fig. 7 (a) Temperature dependence of the relative permittivity, (b) maximum dielectric permittivity at 43.6
23 °C and (c) room temperature (~ 24 °C) relative permittivity and dielectric loss of BT-11BS ceramics
24 measured at 1 kHz as a function of the sintering temperature, and (d) as a function of the grain size
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27 Fig. 8 Temperature dependence of relative permittivity of BT-11BS ceramics at various frequencies (100
28 Hz – 500 kHz)
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30 Fig. 9 Inverse dielectric constant vs temperature for BT-11BS ceramics sintered at different temperatures
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32 Fig. 10 (a) Quasi-static direct piezoelectric constant, (b) frequency dependent small signal piezoelectric
33 constant, and (c) planar coupling coefficient and mechanical quality factor for BT-11BS ceramics as a
34 function of sintering temperature
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37 Fig. 11 (a) Quasi-static direct piezoelectric constant and (b) frequency dependent small signal piezoelectric
38 constant as a function of grain size
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40 Fig. 12 (a) Displacement vs. voltage, and (b) normalization coefficient against sintering temperature) for
41 BT-11BS ceramics
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Declaration of interest

We declare that there is no financial or personal interest that could affect the objectivity of this article and there is no competing conflict of any nature.

Preprint
Version

Table 1. Rietveld refinement results of BT-11BS ceramics sintered at different temperatures

Sintering temperature (°C)	1380		1400		1420		1440	
Crystal structure	<i>T</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>C</i>
Space group	<i>P4mm</i>	<i>Pm$\bar{3}$m</i>	<i>P4mm</i>	<i>Pm$\bar{3}$m</i>	<i>P4mm</i>	<i>Pm$\bar{3}$m</i>	<i>P4mm</i>	<i>Pm$\bar{3}$m</i>
Phase content (%)	81.24	18.76	67.83	32.17	67.15	32.85	49.24	50.76
<i>Lattice parameters</i>								
a (Å)	4.0035	4.0201	4.0022	4.0194	4.0085	4.0190	4.0130	4.0168
c (Å)	4.0302	-	4.0294	-	4.0246	-	4.0176	-
c/a	1.0067	-	1.0068	-	1.0040	-	1.0012	-
Angle (°)	$\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90$							
V(Å ³)	64.60	64.97	64.54	64.94	64.67	64.91	64.70	64.81
<i>Fitting errors</i>								
Rwp (%)	14.8		15.3		17.8		16.2	
χ^2	2.54		2.11		3.28		2.45	

T: tetragonal; *C*: cubic.

Table 2. Optical properties of BT-11BS ceramics in visible light spectrum (at 600 nm)

Sintering temperature (°C)	Thickness (mm)	n (-)	k (-)	T (%)	T _{th} * (%)	R (%)	α (10 ⁵ cm ⁻¹)
1380	0.50	2.00	0.31	19.51	78.4	12.1	6.5
	0.97			7.52			
1400	0.50	2.18	0.25	17.39	74.9	14.4	5.2
	0.82			8.22			
1420	0.50	2.16	0.24	15.2	75.5	13.9	5.0
	1.00			4.66			
1440	0.50	2.20	0.20	16.28	74.9	14.1	4.3
	0.89			7.23			

* Theoretical transmittance calculated for thickness 0.5 mm.

Figure 1

Figure 2

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Figure 11

Figure 12

